

Insights of the proton transport efficiency of a membrane electrode assembly by operando monitoring of the local proton concentration during water oxidation

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Experimental

Materials:

The membrane electrode assembly (MEA) was purchased from QuinTech eK, CCM-E-05-NM117, with Nafion-117 as the proton conducting membrane. The cathode layer has a Pt loading of 1 mg cm^{-2} , while the anode layer has an Ir loading of 2 mg cm^{-2} . All chemicals were purchased from Sigma Aldrich with > 99 % purity. Solutions were prepared with the as-received chemicals in distilled water (0.055 mS cm^{-1}). The local pH experiments were conducted with in-house SECM system and a Au ultra-microelectrode (UME).

Pretreatment of the MEA

Prior to the local pH measurements on the Ir side of the MEA (anode side), the as-received MEA was cut into $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ pieces and soaked in $2 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ for two days to maximize the proton transport efficiency. Thereafter, the MEA was thoroughly washed with pure water until the pH of the washing solution turned neutral. Then the MEA was soaked overnight in ultra-pure water. Before the local pH measurements, the MEA was assembled in a custom-made SECM cell exposing a total area of 0.2 cm^2 . Morphological evaluation of the anode and cathode sides of the MEA was done by using a Quanta 3D FEG scanning electron microscope (SEM) (FEI) operated at 30.0 kV.

Long-term operation and poisoning of the MEA

The MEA was subjected to cycles of shutdown and restart conditions by conducting electrolysis at a current density of 50 mA cm^{-2} for 3 days. Subsequently, the MEA was used for local pH measurements.

To induce the membrane degradation, a Fenton's process was adopted where the generated hydroxyl radicals can break the membrane backbone thereby diminishing its proton conductivity. Doing so, acidified Fe^{2+} solution was prepared by dissolving 0.01 M FeCl_2 in $0.01 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$. The MEA was immersed in 4 mL of this solution, and then 1 mL of 30% H_2O_2 was added. Given the rapid decomposition of H_2O_2 in the presence of the Pt catalysts on the cathode side of the MEA, 1 mL of H_2O_2 was supplemented every 30 min . The degradation/poisoning process was conducted for three different durations: 2 hours ,

24 hours, and 1 week, resulting in MEA samples being labeled as MEA-F1, MEA-F2, and MEA-F3 respectively. Following the degradation procedure, the MEA was soaked in 1 M H₂SO₄ for 2 hours to remove any excess iron species from the surface. The digital photograph of the different stages during the poisoning steps are shown in **Figure S6**. Thereafter the local pH measurements were conducted on the Ir side of the MEA in DI water.

Calibrating the pH dependence of the AuO_x reduction peak of an Au UME

The calibration of Au UME as a function of the proton concentration was established by recording the potentiodynamic responses of a Au UME (tip diameter: 10 μm) in perchloric acid with proton concentrations ranging from 97 μM to 9.7 M, specifically including 97 μM, 970 μM, 9.7 mM, 97 mM, 0.97 M, 2.72 M, 4.2 M, 6.7 M, and 9.7 M. The solutions were prepared by diluting from 11.7 M HClO₄. The actual proton concentrations were determined by titrating the solutions with a 0.1 M KOH solution. More details on the titration process can be found in a previous report.¹ Cyclic voltammetry of the Au tip was conducted in a three electrode system and repeated for three times in each calibration solution. A calibration curve was derived from the peak potentials of the Au-O_x reduction peak.

SECM-based local pH measurement

A home-built scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) setup, housed within a Faraday cage, was used for the local pH measurements. A photograph of the SECM setup for the local pH measurement can be found in Figure S2a. The walls of the cage were isolated with vacuumed polystyrene panels (Vaku Isotherm) to minimize temperature fluctuations. Vibrational noise was restricted using an actively damped table (Newport RS 2000). The calibration curves and local pH measurements were conducted at 20 °C and at ambient pressure.

Local pH measurements on the anode side (Ir) of the MEA were conducted by positioning the Au UME in close proximity to the Ir catalyst surface of the MEA. This was achieved by performing a negative feedback SECM approach. The approach curve was recorded using the polarized Au UME (-450 mV vs. Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl) for O₂ reduction in O₂-saturated 1 mM HClO₄ electrolyte. The diffusional access of O₂ is hindered as the tip approaches the electrode-electrolyte interface, resulting in a decrease of the tip current. Once the tip current reaches a minimum, the approach is stopped, and the position is fixed for further experiments. The working distance for the local pH monitoring is ~10 μm.

The measurement protocol for monitoring the local pH during MEA operation comprises verification of the functionality of the Au UME after completing the electrochemical approach by means of a CV at a scan rate of 200 mV s⁻¹ in water or buffer medium (0.1 M potassium phosphate buffer) using a Pt mesh as the counter electrode and a Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl as reference electrode. Then, the anode side of the MEA which is connected as working electrode 2 and is polarized by applying different potentials starting from 0.5 to 2.0 V vs. Ag/AgCl/3M KCl (specifically 0.5, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8, and 2.0 V). At each of these substrate potentials CVs were recorded at the Au UME. The measurements were repeated until the Au-O_x reduction peak was stable. Before moving to a higher substrate potential, a resting potential of 0.5 V vs. Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl was applied, and the electrolyte was flushed to remove the locally produced protons from the preceding measurements. Finally, the peak potentials of the Au-O_x reduction

were converted to proton concentrations/pH values based on the calibration curve (**Figure S3a**). The peak potential values of Au-O_x reduction which were obtained outside the calibration window are shown as $\Delta E_{\text{Au-O}_x/\text{Au}}$ (**Figure S3b**). For this a relative shift in the Au-O_x/Au reduction peak potential was calculated, from the peak potentials observed during polarization of the sample at a resting potential ($V_{\text{rest}} = 1.19 \text{ V vs. RHE}$).

Figure S1. SEM images of the (a) anode side (iridium) and (b) cathode side (Pt-based catalyst) of the MEA.

Figure S2. (a) SECM cell setup for local pH measurements (b) on operating MEA samples.

Figure S3. (a) Calibration curve derived from peak potential of the Au-O_x reduction at a Au UME. (b) Voltammetric response of the Au UME as a function of the applied potential at the anode side of the MEA.

Figure S3a shows a calibration curve correlating the of Au-O_x reduction process at the Au UME with different proton concentrations. Two different slopes are observed in the investigated concentration regime, namely 63 mV dec⁻¹ for H⁺ concentrations between 97 μM to 0.97 M, and 250 mV dec⁻¹ for higher H⁺ concentrations up to 9.7 M. Within this calibration window no change in the thermodynamically stable Au/Au-O_x phase occurs and hence the dependency of the Au/Au-O_x redox potential on the H⁺ and H₂O activity determines the observed peak potential shift,¹ as predicted from Eq. S1. Here, the tip response was correlated with the H⁺ concentration from the calibration. The significantly increased slope at highly acidic conditions can be explained by a notable increase in the H⁺ activity coefficient, where the protons cannot be completely solvated because the available free water molecules become locally limiting. Concordantly, the water activity becomes less than unity in concentrated HClO₄ solutions.²

$$E_{\text{Au}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Au}} = E_0 - \frac{RT}{6F} \ln \frac{a(\text{Au})^2 a(\text{H}_2\text{O})^3}{a(\text{Au}_2\text{O}_3) \cdot a(\text{H}^+)^6} \quad (\text{Eq. S2})$$

During the measurement of the local pH imposed by polarization of the MEA anode to OER potentials, the peak potential of the Au-O_x changed to a range indicating a far-from-neutral pH condition, which is outside the definition of the pH. As seen in Eq. S2, the activities of water and protons must be considered to describe the Au-oxide reduction potential. For this reason and with the aim to not mislead the reader, we have used the peak potential change ($\Delta E_{\text{Au-O}_x/\text{Au}}$) as a local indicator for the OER-dependent acidification.

Figure S4. (a) SEM images of the Au microelectrode tip used for local pH measurements; (b) shows the zoomed version of a confirming the diameter of the Au probe.

Figure S5. (a) Substrate potential-dependent current density, and (b) changes in local proton concentration in dependence on the anode potential. Experiments were performed in buffered and unbuffered conditions using a pristine MEA polarized vs. a Pt counter electrode positioned inside the anolyte (Pt_{ext}).

Figure S6. Changes in the local proton concentration as a function of the applied potential on the anode side of the MEA. The counter electrode is the MEA cathode (Pt) separated by the membrane from the polarized anode.

Figure S7. Galvanostatic activation protocol of the MEA.

Figure S8. A MEA (a) during Fenton's process (in acidified Fe ions solution, pH 2). b) After the Fenton's process, and (c) after cleaning with 1 M H_2SO_4 to remove excess of iron species from the MEA.

Fenton's method is the most widely used degradation protocol for producing free radicals where H_2O_2 and Fe ions react to form hydroxyl and hydroperoxyl radicals (Eq. S3 and S4).³⁻⁵ The stability of the membrane is affected by the attack of these radicals at different sites of PFSA chains in Nafion.

Table S1. Summary of experimental indicators obtained in the study.

Experimental indicators when E _{sub} changed from 1.08 V to 2.58 V					
MEA conditions	SECM cell configuration	Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	ΔE _{Au-OxAu} (mV)	Proton concentration	Proton transport performance of MEA
Pristine MEA in water	non-zero gap electrolyzer	from 0 to 1.1	1386	from 10 ⁻⁵ to >11.1 M	good
	zero gap electrolyzer	0 to 74.5	61	10 ⁻¹ to 0.27 M	
Activated MEA in water	zero gap electrolyzer	0 to 216	-58	10 ⁻² to 0.028 M	good
Pristine MEA in buffer	non-zero gap electrolyzer	0 to 8.2	1063	10 ⁻³ to >11.1 M	-
MEA-Fenton process- 2 h	zero gap electrolyzer	0 to 31.4	43	10 ⁻² to 0.045 M	good
MEA-Fenton process- 24 h		0 to 22.1	-62	10 ⁻² to 0.017 M	good
MEA-Fenton process-1 week		0 to 28	209	10 ⁻³ to 0.189	damaged

Local proton concentration was determined by positioning the Au UME at the vicinity of the IrO₂ side of an operating MEA. MEAs were treated at different experimental conditions and polarized from 1.08 V to 2.58 V vs. RHE.

References

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